

“Biosecurity Updates, Challenges and Opportunities in the Animal Sector”

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OVERVIEW

Types of farm biosecurity

Updates on farm biosecurity

Opportunities on farm biosecurity

References

Lab biosafety vs. lab biosecurity vs. farm biosecurity

General farm biosecurity practice

Challenges on farm biosecurity

Key messages

Objectives

- To differentiate lab biosafety & biosecurity from farm biosecurity;
- To enumerate the different types of farm biosecurity;
- To identify several farm biosecurity practices;
- To be abreast on the latest farm biosecurity practices; and
- To know the challenges and opportunities on farm biosecurity

Definition

- Biosafety - containment principles, technologies and practices implemented to prevent unintentional exposure to biological agents on their inadvertent release
- Biosecurity - principles, technologies and practices implemented for the protection, control and accountability of biological materials and/or the equipment, skills and data related to their handling. Biosecurity aims to prevent their unauthorized access, loss, theft, misuse, diversion or release.

- WHO, 2020

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- WHO, 2020

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- WHO, 2020

Definition

- Laboratory biosecurity - principles, technologies and practices implemented for the protection, control and accountability of biological materials and/or the equipment, skills and data related to their handling. Biosecurity aims to **prevent their unauthorized access, loss, theft, misuse, diversion or release**.

- WHO, 2020

- Farm biosecurity - a set of management and physical measures designed to **reduce the risk of introduction, establishment and spread of animal diseases, infections or infestations to, from and within an animal population**.

- OIE Terrestrial Animal Health Code, 2018

Types of farm biosecurity

- Structural biosecurity
 - concerns the design of the farm and buildings to have efficiency in work, sanitation and disinfection
 - ✓ **Gates**, fences, and their regular maintenance
 - ✓ Gate signages

Fig 1. Gate signage of Level 1 biosecurity compliant farms (small hold)

Types of farm biosecurity

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 - concerns the design of the farm and buildings to have efficiency in work, sanitation and disinfection
 - ✓ Gates, fences, and their regular maintenance
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Fig 1. Gate signage of Level 1 biosecurity compliant farms (small hold)

Types of farm biosecurity

- Operational biosecurity
 - points involved with the daily running of the site
 1. Biological biosecurity measures
 2. Chemical biosecurity measures

Biological biosecurity measures

- Farm location
 - Away from the highway and far from the neighbouring houses
- Traffic control
 - ❖ Vehicle
 - ✓ Outside vehicles - not allowed to enter
 - ✓ Inside vehicles - limit access to sensitive areas

Biological biosecurity measures

- Traffic control

- ❖ Human

- ✗ Unnecessary visits
 - ✗ Walk-in visits
 - ✗ Sick visitors
 - ✓ Appointment system
 - ✓ Morning visits only
 - ✓ Log-in/log-out (logbook) system
 - ✓ Limit some areas to guests
 - ✓ Always follow the designated tour route

Fig 2. Sample logbooks for record keeping

Chemical biosecurity measures

- Disinfectants
 - ✓ Glutaraldehyde
 - ✓ Sodium hypochlorite
 - ✓ Chlorine
 - ✓ Limestone
 - ❖ Vehicle baths*
 - ❖ Foot baths**
 - Dips
 - Power sprayer
 - ❖ Sanitation stations**
 - ❖ Disinfection facility*
- * Farm entrance
** Building entrance

Fig 3. Foot dip using a stainless steel vat with rubber matting situated at the entrance of a building.

General farm biosecurity practices

Four major levels of biosecurity principles and practice

1. Small farm biosecurity for smallholder livestock owners,

2. Village-level biosecurity for smallholder livestock,

3. Biosecurity for the commercial enterprise livestock sector,

4. National biosecurity programmes for safer regional trade of livestock and their products

General farm biosecurity practices

Principles of biosecurity

- 1) **Livestock quarantine and animal movements.** Manage the introduction and movement of livestock in a way that minimises the risk of introducing or spreading infectious disease.
- 2) **People, equipment and vehicle hygiene.** People, equipment and vehicles entering the village, enterprise or country are controlled to minimise the potential for property contamination.
- 3) **Food and water safety.** Quality of stock feed and water is fit for purpose, especially purchased feed that is free from contaminants, untreated swill and/or restricted animal material (i.e. feeds containing ruminant tissue cannot be fed to ruminants).
- 4) **Animal health management, surveillance and reporting.** Prevent and control animal disease by using appropriate vaccination programmes, regularly monitoring for disease and immediately reporting outbreaks of TADs.
- 5) **Public awareness.** All farmers, traders, agency staff and contractors, understand the importance of the biosecurity requirements for the village, enterprise or country in which they work and can implement the agreed practices for which they are responsible.

General farm biosecurity practices

- New stocks
 - ✓ Acquire stocks from disease-free herds or from credible farms.
 - ✓ Quarantine animals for 30-60 days.
 - ✓ Allow a distance of at least 10 meters from the main bird flock or 100 meters from the main herd
 - ✓ Allocate own personnel and paraphernalia for the quarantine herd, if possible.
 - ✓ Maintain healthy new stocks.
 - ✓ Maintain clean vehicles, and facilities.

General farm biosecurity practices

- Cleaning and sanitation
 - Prevention measures
 - ✓ 1-2x daily removal of debris on feeders, waterers, enclosures, & flooring
 - ✓ 1x/week disinfection
 - ✓ Disinfection down time is for at least 14 days.
 - ✓ Keep areas dry.
 - ✓ Keep grass surrounding buildings low.
 - ✓ Proper waste management
 - ✓ Clean and disinfect vehicles before entrance to the farm
 - Control measures
 - ✓ Daily disinfection

General farm biosecurity practices

- Animal health

- Maintain healthy stocks.
- Practice an “All-In, All Out” system
- Identify and isolate sick animals immediately.
- Practice using one-use disposable needles per animal.
- Vector and vermin control

Apply sand surrounding buildings to prevent entry of rodents.

Fig 4. Mesh size for vector control can be 1/4”.

General farm biosecurity practices

- Animal health
 - Regular water sanitation and treatment
 - Feeds storage management
 - Proper record keeping
 - Use of PPE
 - Proper disposal of carcass

Fig 5. Storage bins for feeds

General farm biosecurity practices

- Personnel

- Maintain proper personal hygiene.
- Maintain a healthy workforce.
- Identify and isolate the sick immediately.
- Use of PPE
- Limit access of personnel to restricted areas

Fig 6. Farm personnel using PPE
- boots, gloves, caps and
overalls

General farm biosecurity practices

- After a farm visit....
 - Leave all farm belongings.
 - Brush footwear at the scrubbing area and return in situ.
 - Practice handwashing and disinfection.
 - If with vehicles, pass by the disinfection facility.
 - Have your car washed.
 - Practice 24-hour downtime before entering another farm.

Fig 7. Active washing and scrubbing of footwear before leaving the farm

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification (BAI Memo Circular No. 20 Series of 2022)
 - provides guidance on the biosecurity min. standards

❖ Purposes

- ✓ To ensure prevention of animal diseases
- ✓ To continue animal raising in their areas.
Only those farms with LEVEL 1 Biosecurity are given the permit to carry on animal raising.
- ✓ To be eligible as recipient of agriculture-related projects of the government.
- ✓ To be excluded in mandatory stamping out during disease outbreak.

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification

- ❖ Area of coverage

- ✓ Location
 - ✓ Facilities
 - ✓ Records
 - ✓ Vehicle movements

- ❖ Biosecurity levels

- ✓ 1 (Small hold farms)
 - ✓ 2 (Commercial farms)

Fig 8. Small hold piggery

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for level 1

1. **LOCATION:** Clearly demarcated clean and dirty line (CDL); with fence
FACILITIES:
2. Shower In/Out (w/ soap & shampoo); drainage away from the farm
3. Complete change of clothes and dedicated boots to enter farm
4. Observes min. person downtime
5. No pork or pork products from outside
6. Feed bags **DISALLOWED** to enter high-security area (HSA)
7. Swill and kitchen wastes **NOT FED** to pigs
8. **RECORDS:** Viajeros, visitors **DISALLOWED** in load-out
9. **MOVEMENT:** Outside vehicles **DISALLOWED** inside the farm

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for level 1

1. **LOCATION:** Clearly demarcated clean and dirty line (CDL); with fence

- ✓ Regulates human traffic
- ✓ Prevents theft
- ✓ Prevents disease transmission

Fig 9. Flat sheet perimeter fence to clearly separate the outside of the farm

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for level 1

FACILITIES:

2. Shower In/Out (w/ soap & shampoo); drainage away from the farm
3. Complete change of clothes and dedicated boots to enter farm

Figs 10-11. Farm signages on biosecurity involving human entry to farm facilities

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for level 1

FACILITIES:

4. Observes min. person downtime

- ✓ At least 1 night before entry
- ✓ Avoid going to other farms or wet markets before entry to the farm

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...
 - ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for level 1

FACILITIES:

5. No pork or pork products from outside

The poster is a multi-sectioned informational graphic. At the top left, it reads "DON'T BRING PORK AND PROCESSED PRODUCTS LIKE SAUSAGES, HAMS ETC. TO THE PHILIPPINES" in bold blue and red text, followed by "IT WILL BE CONFISCATED AT THE AIRPORT TO PREVENT SPREAD OF AFRICAN SWINE FEVER". Below this, it lists "COUNTRIES AFFECTED WITH ASF: BELGIUM, BULGARIA, CZECH REPUBLIC, HUNGARY, LATVIA, MOLDOVA, POLAND, ROMANIA, RUSSIA, SOUTH AFRICA, UKRAINE, ZAMBIA, CHINA, VIETNAM, MONGOLIA, CAMBODIA, HONGKONG, NORTH KOREA". The bottom left features a pig and the slogan "EAT PINOY PORK SUPPORT OUR FARMERS" with logos for FDA, MNL, and other agencies. The top right section is titled "IMPORTANT ADVISORY TO PREVENT AFRICAN SWINE FEVER (ASF)" and shows "STRICTLY PROHIBITED" with icons of meat products crossed out. The middle right section lists "TO AVOID INCONVENIENCE AND FINES" with two numbered steps: "1 GET SANITARY PHYTOSANITARY (SPS) import clearance" and "2 FOLLOW veterinary inspection protocols". It also states "Products without permits will be confiscated by Veterinary Quarantine Officers" and cites "Republic Act 10611, DA AO 9 Series of 2010". The bottom right section says "HELP KEEP ANIMAL DISEASES OUT OF THE PHILIPPINES! HAVE A SAFE AND ENJOYABLE TRIP!" and provides contact information for the Department of Agriculture, Bureau of Animal Industry, including a telephone number, email, website, and Facebook page.

Fig 12. Inter-agency poster on prohibition of entry of pork and pork products to the country.

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for level 1

FACILITIES:

6. Feed bags **DISALLOWED** to enter high-security area (HSA)
 - Presence of control system for feed bags before entry to pig area

Fig 13. Farm signage on biosecurity involving entry of feeds to farm facilities

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...
 - ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for level 1

FACILITIES:

7. Swill and kitchen wastes NOT FED to pigs

- **BAWAL MAGPAKAIN NG KANING BABOY.**

Fig 14. Farm signage on biosecurity involving entry of pork products to farm facilities

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for level 1

- 8. **RECORDS:** Viajeros, visitors **DISALLOWED** in load-out

- BAWAL PUMASOK ang sinuman na walang pahintulot.
- Huwag pupunta sa farm sa loob ng 24 oras kung galing sa ibang farm.

Fig 15. Farm signage on biosecurity involving human traffic to farm facilities

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for level 1

- 9. **MOVEMENT:** Outside vehicles **DISALLOWED** inside the farm

Fig 16. Farm signage on biosecurity involving vehicles to farm facilities

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...
 - ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for Level 2

FACILITIES:

10. Pest control program in place
11. Supplies decontamination facility (farm and personal)
12. Water chlorinated and regularly tested for contamination

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...
 - ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for Level 2

FACILITIES:

10. Pest control program in place

- Paghiwalayin ang magkakaibang uri ng hayop at huwag hayaang gumala ang mga ito.
- Kontrolin ang pagpasok ng ligaw na hayop, peste, at insekto.

Fig 17. Farm signage on biosecurity involving pest control on farm facilities

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...
 - ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for Level 2

FACILITIES:

10. Pest control program in place

- Bird-proofing - to prevent transmission of disease
- Rodent proofing
 1. Install traps and regularly maintain them.
 2. Maintain clean enclosures. Clear grass near pens for at least 3 meters.
 3. Clear trees near pens to prevent entry of rodents

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...
 - ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for Level 2

FACILITIES:

11. Supplies decontamination facility (farm and personal)

- Disinfect food with chlorine or citric acid
- Farm supplies with ozone or fumigant or UV light overnight
- Vaccine bottles wiped with 70% alcohol before storage

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...
 - ❖ Required biosecurity parameters for Level 2

Fig. 18. Piglet drinking from a nipple drinker.

FACILITIES:

12. Water chlorinated and regularly tested for contamination

- No chlorine in water at times of oral vaccination
- No chlorine in water if water line with acidifier or probiotics

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Non-mandatory biosecurity parameters

1. **LOCATION:** Distance from the nearest farm - > 500m (standard)

FACILITIES:

2. Signage of Biosecure area / Biosecurity procedures to follow

3. Regular cleaning and disinfection

4. No food/drinks in high-security area (HSA)/pig area

5. Load-in/ load-out (1-way); cleaned and disinfected after each use

6. Dead animal disposal - covered

7. **RECORDS:** Visitor's log; mortality records; written biosecurity procedures

8. **VEHICLE:** Dedicated feed trucks or feed carts used inside the farm ONLY

9. **MOVEMENT:** Trucks washed and disinfected before entry to farm

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Non-mandatory biosecurity parameters

LOCATION: Distance from the nearest farm - > 500m (standard)

Fig 19. Aerial footage showing the distance of nearby animal farms

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Non-mandatory biosecurity parameters

FACILITIES:

- ✓ Signage of Biosecure area / Biosecurity procedures to follow

Ang sumusunod na **TAKDANG HAKBANG NG BIOSECURITY** ay mahigpit na ipinatutupad sa **FARM** na ito upang labanan ang African Swine Fever at iba pang sakit ng baboy:

- BAWAL PUMASOK ang sinuman na walang pahintulot.
• Huwag pupunta sa farm sa loob ng 24 oras kung galing sa ibang farm.
- BAWAL MAGPAKAIN NG KANING BABOY.
- Ang mga sasakyan ay hanggang sa labas lamang ng farm.
- Ang feeds na bagong deliver ay isalin ng lalagyan bago ipasok sa loob ng farm.
- Paghiwalayin ang magkakaibang uri ng hayop at huwag hayaang gumala ang mga ito.
• Kontrolin ang pagpasok ng ligaw na hayop, peste, at insekto.
- Itala sa record book ang lahat ng pumapasok sa loob ng farm.
- Maligo at magpalit ng kasuotan at sapatos bago pumasok sa loob ng farm.
- Ibukod at itapon nang maayos ang mga dumi at namatay na hayop.
- Tumapak sa Foot Bath bago pumasok sa kulungan ng baboy.
- Linisin ang kulungan ng baboy araw araw at magdisinfect ayon sa schedule (isa o dalawang beses sa loob ng isang lingo).
• Magdisinfect ng mga suplay at kagamitan bago ipasok sa loob ng farm.

Para sa inyong pagtalima. MARAMING SALAMAT PO

HATID NG: **BANTAY ASF SA BARANGAY** SA PAKIKIPAGTULUNGAN NG:

Figs 20-21. Farm biosecurity signage at entrance and inter-agency farm biosecurity guidelines

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Non-mandatory biosecurity parameters

- FACILITIES:**

- ✓ Regular cleaning and disinfection

- Linisin ang kulungan ng baboy araw araw at magdisinfect ayon sa schedule (isa o dalawang beses sa loob ng isang lingo).
- Magdisinfect ng mga suplay at kagamitan bago ipasok sa loob ng farm.

Fig 22. Farm signage on biosecurity involving sanitation and disinfection of farm facilities

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Non-mandatory biosecurity parameters

- FACILITIES:**

- ✓ No food/drinks in high-security area (HSA) / animal area

Figs 23-24. Farm biosecurity signage prohibiting food in the animal pens.

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Non-mandatory biosecurity parameters

- FACILITIES:**

- ✓ Load-in/ load-out (1-way); cleaned and disinfected after each use

Fig 25. In-house feeds wagon used to transport feeds from outside

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Non-mandatory biosecurity parameters

- FACILITIES:**

- ✓ Dead animal disposal - covered

Fig 26. Farm signage on biosecurity involving waste management

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Non-mandatory biosecurity parameters

- RECORDS:**

- ✓ Visitor's log; mortality records; written biosecurity procedures

- Itala sa record book ang lahat ng pumapasok sa loob ng farm.

Fig 27. Farm signage on biosecurity involving proper record keeping

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Non-mandatory biosecurity parameters

- VEHICLE:**

- ✓ Dedicated feed trucks or feed carts used inside the farm ONLY

Fig 28. Designated feeds tractor used to deliver customized mixed ration.

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...
 - ❖ Non-mandatory biosecurity parameters
- MOVEMENT:**
- ✓ Trucks washed and disinfected before entry to farm

Fig 29. Vehicle disinfection facility in ITCPH, Batangas

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...

- ❖ Scoring based on risk level

- ✓ High risk (0 point)
- ✓ Moderate risk (1 point)
- ✓ Low risk (2 points)

- ❖ A score of 0 in any of the required parameters will disqualify the farm on a particular level.

Updates on farm biosecurity

- Farm biosecurity classification...
 - ❖ Min. scores of compliance
 - ✓ Level 1 - 18 points
 - ✓ Level 2 - 24 points
 - ❖ Target score - 42 points
 - ✓ Low risk level
 - ✓ Farm is 100% compliant to all biosecurity standards
 - ❖ Goal - Farms must at least have Biosecurity Level 1

Annex A. Farm Biosecurity Matrix Evaluation and Classification

DESCRIPTION		CLASSIFICATION				
		Standard	Target Score	LEVEL 0	LEVEL 1	LEVEL 2
Location	Distance from the nearest pig farm	>500 m	2			
	Clearly demarcated CDL (clean & dirty line); WITH FENCE	yes	2		2	2
Facilities	Signage of Biosecure Area/ biosecurity procedures to follow	yes	2			
	Shower In/Out (w/soap & shampoo); drainage away from farm*	yes	2	0	2	2
	Complete change of clothes & dedicated boots to enter farm	yes	2	0	2	2
	Pest control program in place	yes	2			2
	Regular cleaning & disinfection	yes	2			
	Observes minimum downtime**	yes	2	0	2	2
	Supplies decontamination facility (farm & personal)***	yes	2			2
	Food items (no pork, pork products from outside)	yes	2		2	2
	No food/drinks in HAS/pig area	yes	2			
	Water chlorinated & regularly tested for contamination	yes	2			2
	Load-in/load-out (1way); cleaned & disinfected after each use	yes	2			
	Feed bags ALLOWED to enter HAS****	NO	2	0	2	2
	Swill & kitchen wastes (kanin baboy, lamaw) FED to pigs	NO	2		2	2
	Dead pig disposal - covered	YES	2			
Records	Visitors log; mortality record; written biosecurity procedures	yes	2			
	Viajeros, visitors ALLOWED in load-out	NO	2	0	2	2
Vehicle	Dedicated feed trucks or feed carts used inside farm ONLY	yes	2			
Movement	Trucks washed & disinfected before entry to pig farm	yes	2			
	Outside vehicles ALLOWED in farm	NO	2	0	2	2
BEST SCORE (100% COMPLIANT)			42			
Minimum Compliance Score				18	24	

*before entry to HSA (best practice -shower before entry to MSA)
 ** at least 1 night before entry to the farm
 *** disinfect food with chlorine or citric acid; farm supplies with ozone, or fumigant or UV light overnite; vaccine bottles wiped w/ 70% alcohol before storage
 **** pelleted feed only (best with mitigants; feed bags not allowed to enter HAS

RISK LEVEL	SCORE
High	0
Moderate	1
Low	2

NOTE: Score in yellow box is default score; any score below default score is automatic FAIL and farm will be classified in lower level

Source: Video Training for BaBay ASF. 2020. Farm Biosecurity Evaluation & Classification. File can be requested from Philippine College of Swine Practitioners

FARM BIOSECURITY EVALUATION FORM

Region: _____ Province: _____ Date of Visit: _____
 City/Municipality: _____ Date of Next Visit: _____

I. FARM PROFILE

FARM NAME:	FARM OWNER:
ADDRESS (BRGY):	CONTACT NUMBER:
Longitude: _____ Latitude: _____	FARM VETERINARIAN/CONSULTANT:
TYPE OF OPERATION: <input type="checkbox"/> farrow to finish <input type="checkbox"/> piglet production <input type="checkbox"/> grow-out <input type="checkbox"/> contract growing <input type="checkbox"/> paiwi	

ANIMAL INVENTORY

SWINE:

Boar	Sow/Gilts	Piglets	Weanlings	Fatteners	Native

OTHER ANIMALS (indicate no. of heads in the blank space)

Cattle: _____ Carabao: _____ Goat: _____ Horse: _____
 Layer: _____ Broiler: _____ Gamefowl: _____ Native: _____
 Ducks: _____ Dog: _____ Cat: _____ Rabbit: _____
 Other animals: (specify) _____

II. BIOSECURITY STANDARDS

	DESCRIPTION	STANDARD	RESPONSE	SCORE
LOCATION	Distance from the nearest pig farm	>500m		
	Clearly Demarcated CDL (clean & dirty line); with FENCE	YES		
FACILITIES	Signage of Biosecure Area / Biosecurity procedures to follow	YES		
	Shower In/Out (w/ soap & shampoo); drainage away from farm *	YES		
	Complete change of clothes & dedicated boots to enter farm	YES		
	Pest control program in place	YES		
	Regular cleaning and disinfection	YES		
	Observes minimum downtime**	YES		
	Supplies decontamination facility (farm & personal) ***	YES		
	Food items (no pork, pork products from outside)	YES		
	No food/drinks in high security area (HSA)/pig area	YES		
	Water chlorinated & regularly tested for contamination	YES		
	Load-in / load-out (1 way); cleaned & disinfected after each use	YES		
	Feed bags ALLOWED to enter HSA/pig area****	NO		
Swill & kitchen wastes (kanin baboy, lamaw) FED to pigs	NO			
Dead pig disposal - covered	YES			
RECORDS	Visitors log, mortality record, written biosecurity procedures	YES		
	Viajeros, visitors ALLOWED in load-out	NO		
VEHICLE	Dedicated feed truck or feed carts used inside farm ONLY	YES		
MOVEMENT	Trucks washed & disinfected before entry to pig farm	YES		
	Outside vehicles ALLOWED in farm	NO		

LEGEND:

* before entry to HSA (best practice-shower before entry to MSA)

** at least 1 night before entry to farm

*** disinfect food with chlorine or citric acid; farm supplies with ozone or fumigant

or UV light overnight; vaccine bottles wiped with 70% alcohol before storage

**** pelleted feed only (best with mitigants; feed bags not allowed to enter HSA)

_____ DEFAULT for LEVEL 1;

_____ and _____ DEFAULT for LEVEL 2

TOTAL SCORE:

BIOSECURITY LEVEL:

BEST SCORE: 42

MINIMUM COMPLIANCE SCORE:

LEVEL 1 = 18 LEVEL 2 = 24

NOTE: Response similar to the standard can get a score of 2, otherwise, the score is 0.
 Farm with 0 score in the DEFAULT field will be classified in lower level.

RECOMMENDATION: _____

Consented by: _____

Inspected by: _____

Noted by: _____

 Farm Owner / Representative
 (Signature above printed name)

 Biosecurity Officer
 (Signature above printed name)

 Head of Office - OPV/CVO/MAO
 (Signature above printed name)

FARM BIOSECURITY EVALUATION FORM

Region: _____ Province: _____ Date of Visit: _____
 City/Municipality: _____ Date of Next Visit: _____

I. FARM PROFILE

FARM NAME:	FARM OWNER:
ADDRESS (BRGY):	CONTACT NUMBER:
Longitude: _____ Latitude: _____	FARM VETERINARIAN/CONSULTANT:
TYPE OF OPERATION: <input type="checkbox"/> farrow to finish <input type="checkbox"/> piglet production <input type="checkbox"/> grow-out <input type="checkbox"/> contract growing <input type="checkbox"/> paiwi	

ANIMAL INVENTORY

SWINE:

Boar	Sow/Gilts	Piglets	Weanlings	Fatteners	Native

OTHER ANIMALS *(indicate no. of heads in the blank space)*

Cattle: _____ Carabao: _____ Goat: _____ Horse: _____
 Layer: _____ Broiler: _____ Gamefowl: _____ Native: _____
 Ducks: _____ Dog: _____ Cat: _____ Rabbit: _____
 Other animals: *(specify)* _____

Fig 32. Demographics and animal data listed at the top of the farm biosecurity evaluation form.

II. BIOSECURITY STANDARDS

DESCRIPTION		STANDARD	RESPONSE	SCORE
LOCATION	Distance from the nearest pig farm	>500m	200 m	0
	Clearly Demarcated CDL (clean & dirty line); with FENCE	YES	YES	2
FACILITIES	Signage of Biosecure Area / Biosecurity procedures to follow	YES	YES	2
	Shower In/Out (w/ soap & shampoo); drainage away from farm*	YES	NO	0
	Complete change of clothes & dedicated boots to enter farm	YES	YES	2
	Pest control program in place	YES	NO	0
	Regular cleaning and disinfection	YES	YES	2
	Observes minimum downtime**	YES	YES	2
	Supplies decontamination facility (farm & personal) ***	YES	NO	0
	Food items (no pork, pork products from outside)	YES	YES	2
	No food/drinks in high security area (HSA)/pig area	YES	YES	2
	Water chlorinated & regularly tested for contamination	YES	NO	0
	Load-in / load-out (1 way); cleaned & disinfected after each use	YES	YES	2
	Feed bags ALLOWED to enter HSA/pig area****	NO	NO	2
	Swill & kitchen wastes (kanin baboy, lamaw) FED to pigs	NO	NO	2
	Dead pig disposal - covered	YES	YES	2
RECORDS	Visitors log, mortality record, written biosecurity procedures	YES	YES	2
	Viajeros, visitors ALLOWED in load-out	NO	NO	2
VEHICLE	Dedicated feed truck or feed carts used inside farm ONLY	YES	N/A	-
MOVEMENT	Trucks washed & disinfected before entry to pig farm	YES	N/A	-
	Outside vehicles ALLOWED in farm	NO	NO	2

LEGEND:

- * before entry to HSA (best practice-shower before entry to MSA)
- **at least 1 night before entry to farm
- ***disinfect food with chlorine or citric acid; farm supplies with ozone or fumigant or UV light overnight; vaccine bottles wiped with 70% alcohol before storage
- ****pelleted feed only (best with mitigants; feed bags not allowed to enter HSA)

 DEFAULT for LEVEL 1;
 DEFAULT for LEVEL 2

NOTE: Response similar to the standard can get a score of 2, otherwise, the score is 0.
Farm with 0 score in the DEFAULT field will be classified in lower level.

TOTAL SCORE:

28

BIOSECURITY LEVEL:

0

BEST SCORE: 42

MINIMUM COMPLIANCE SCORE:

LEVEL 1 = 18 LEVEL 2 = 24

RECOMMENDATION: Siguraduhing maligo muna bago magpunta ng farm .

Consented by:

Inspected by:

Noted by:

Farm Owner / Representative

(Signature above printed name)

Biosecurity Officer

(Signature above printed name)

Head of Office - OPV/CVO/MAO

(Signature above printed name)

Challenges on farm biosecurity

1. Poor understanding of biosecurity by personnel
2. Poor compliance
 - ❖ Farm level
 - ❖ Trader engagement
3. Lack of monitoring personnel and experts
4. Delayed or non-reporting of animal diseases
5. Outbreaks (African Swine Fever and Avian Influenza) and the COVID-19 Pandemic

Opportunities on farm biosecurity

1. Promotion of and training on farm biosecurity
 - ❖ Standardization of farm biosecurity protocols
 - ❖ Farm efficiency
2. Closer partnerships with stakeholders and agencies
3. Establishment of pool of experts
4. Innovation and technology (mobile apps, social media, softwares) in surveillance
5. Research
6. Digitalization

Key messages

1. Align farm biosecurity efforts in the livestock production supply chain with the goals and interests of all stakeholders involved and to emphasize measures that bring immediate risk management advantages, thereby generating interest, investment, and practical implementation.
2. It is of prime importance to integrate farm biosecurity and disease control with enhanced livestock productivity and financial gains as can be seen with how the commercial sector operates.
3. These approaches allow sustainable advancements in livelihoods and economic development while also establishing a more efficient strategy for controlling and eradicating disease.

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Thank you for listening

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